

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.sasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Dr. Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela, Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Dr. Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'	Kasthuri P. K.	217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port City	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayanīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणमानम्	डा. राघवेंद्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुरोधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशवमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14683221>

From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port City

Gowri S Panicker¹

The erstwhile Elancon or Kaulam Mall had a commercial fame and reputation from the days of Ancient Rome and Phoenicians. Records and ancient Roman coins recovered from the region mention the existence of the town as a trade link with the Romans, Chinese, Arabs and other Oriental traders. In fact, the name of the city; Kollam itself is believed to have been derived from the corresponding Sanskrit word meaning “pepper” which clearly indicates the importance the town had in the trade map of the world. Most of the historians are of the view that the port existed much before the birth of Jesus Christ as is evident from the writings of Pliny the Elder, who mentions Kollam or Nelcynda along with Muziris as the two main anchoring points of Greek ships in India.

Hoardings of ingots and archaeological evidences pertaining to lower Palaeolithic period and Megalithic period discovered from the vicinity of the port town takes the history of Kollam back to pre-stone age. As southern points of Kerala and Tamil Nadu were the cradle of Sangam culture, it can be perceived that Kollam too would have been a focal point of the civilization.

Heritage

Diverse evidences of archaeological and historical importance have been discovered from different regions of Kollam like, Sasthamcotta, Kadakkal, Kulathupuzha and Mayyanad. A few Megalithic cists have been excavated from the eastern sides and metropolitan areas of the region like from Thazhuthala and a few

1. Research Scholar, Department of History, University of Kerala

lower Palaeolithic tools also have been sighted. Burial chambers, iron implements and earthen vessels are part of some of the archaeological remains that add to the historical significance of the land.

After the dawn of 2nd century C E, Kollam saw the arrival of many explorers, missionaries, apostles and army commanders beginning from Pliny, Saint Thomas, Mar Sabor and Mar Proth. Of these Saint Thomas is believed to have been one of the 12 disciples of Jesus Christ and even though still a strongly contested topic, Christian faith claims that this apostle had visited Kerala including Kollam back in 52 CE and had established seven and a half churches including one in Kollam city near the port which is believed to have been destroyed by the Arabian sea.

825 CE saw the inception of Kollam port at Thangasseri by Mar Sabor and Mar Proth, two East Syriac Bishops who settled in the region with their followers. The port at Thangasseri was commissioned as a substitute to the old inland sea-port that existed near present day Thevalakkara or Neendakara which was known as Nelcynda and Tyndis among the Romans and Greeks and as Thondi to Tamils.

Architectural History

The architectural monuments of Kollam have gone into oblivion; most of them have even disappeared completely not even leaving a trace to identify at least their geographical location. The lack of governmental and expert care is the main reason for their pathetic condition. ‘Panankavu palace’, if had existed would have become the most astonishing architectural monument of Quilon, but unfortunately the historians and archaeologists of Kerala have failed to even identify its location let alone the remains. Some of the other existing monuments of historical importance are;

Thevalli Palace

The palace was constructed so that the king and resident (representative of Viceroy) of Travancore, while visiting Kollam could use it for their stay. It was built by Gouri Parvathy Bhai in 19th century.

Residency Bungalow

The bungalow was constructed in 1810 for the first resident of

Travancore; Colonel Monroe along the banks of river Ashtamudi. The structure is the combination of Kerala and Western architecture. Many important personalities like Lord Curzon, Gandhiji, Nehru and Rajiv Gandhi had stayed in this structure.

Railway palace

The palace was built as a halt for the king and his family members while travelling from Thiruvananthapuram to Madras via train. The materials used for the construction were imported from Paris.

Thangasseri fort

The fort came into existence in 1517 CE at the hands of Portuguese chief Haiter Rodringz, but later it fell into the hands of Dutch forces. But finally, the fort became a standpoint for the British administration. Unfortunately, the fort is under threat from the sea waves.

In addition to these aforementioned monuments Kollam is also known for Kallada palace, Pozhikkara palace, Sree Moolam Picture Palace, Punalur bridge, Sengottai rail line etc. which have given the district an important position in the tourist map of Kerala and India.

Evolvement as the Capital of Venad

The period of 9th to 17th century saw the evolution of Kollam as a world-renowned capital city, port town and trade hub of one of the most powerful kingdoms of Kerala; the Venad. The first epigraphic evidence about the kingdom comes from the 8th century inscription of Pandya ruler Rajapandyan who describes the place as a “beautiful region”. The Venad principality extended initially from Kannetti to Kurakkeni and later on from Kannetti to Thovala, which is often used as a synonym for Kollam. Scholars like Pachu Moothathu opined through his work “Thiruvithamcore Charithram” that Veerakeralan, son of the incommensurable ruler Cheraman Perumal was a ruler of Venad.

Prior to the establishment of Venad, the respective regions were part of the ancient Ay kingdom which ruled over the southern tips of Kerala with Vizhinjam as its capital and trade centre. In fact, regions of present-day Kollam like Perinad, Peruman and Edamon were part of the revenue division of the infamous Parthivapuram

Vishnu Temple. But the intermittent attacks by the Chola rulers on the Ay kingdom and its capital prompted for the inclusion of these regions to Venad.

The development of Venad as an independent kingdom during 12th century was a reaction to the fall of the second Cheras at the hand of the Cholas and hence the last ruler of the Chera faction escaped to South Kerala along with a large army. This last ruler, Rama Verma Kulasekhara settled in Kollam thus establishing Venad. The administrative uniqueness of the principality lies in its system of diarchy which clearly separates the political and religious administration. Panankavu palace served as the administrative headquarters of Venad, but unfortunately the palace has so gone into oblivion and destruction that its present geographical location is still a mystery.

Between 14th and 15th century, the principality started branching out to Thrippappur, Kilimanoor, Kottarakkara and Nedumangad, all of which later became integral vassals and relations of Travancore royal family. Manimangalam inscription of 1046 C E, claims the death of a Venad king at the hands of Chola king Rajaraja Chola. But even after all the recurring attacks the kingdom survived until it was assimilated into Travancore after 17th century.

Through the Words of Foreign Travellers

As a thriving trade centre Kollam was frequently visited by world renowned explorers and traders. Some of the prominent travellers who came and left solid records regarding the features of the Kollam they visited are Sulaiman, Al Beruni, Marco Polo, Abul Fida etc. Both Sulaiman and Al Beruni opined that Kurakkeni Kollam was the most important port of South India and it was the main anchoring point for Persian and Chinese ships. And this is corroborated by the presence of things connected to Chinese and Arabian ethnicity like *Cheenavala*, *Cheenabharani* and places with the name *Chinnakkada* and *Chavara* meaning cemetery. According to them, Kollam was known for building globally acclaimed ships and boats. Moreover, they go on saying that the kingdom was known for its religious harmony between different religions. From their words it can be inferred that by ancient Kollam or Kurakkeni Kollam port, the

records were de facto referring to the present regions of Ashtamudi and Neendakara.

Marco Polo who visited the region discussed in his “Travels of Marco Polo” about the cultural, religious, commercial, agricultural features and regarding the flora and fauna of the land, while Abul Fida opined about the significance of Kollam as an important trade link of the world commercial map. Moroccan explorer Ibn Battutta who visited Kerala during 14th century recorded in his memoir that Kerala had 12 rulers who essayed control over about 30,000 to 50,000 soldiers. He goes on talking about the different ports of Malabar and also about the beauty of Kollam. In addition to them, travelers like Friar Odoric and Jordanus has discussed profoundly about the rituals, customs and farming practices of Kerala.

Instances of Historical Importance

A popular belief that roams around the historical world is that Kollam is mentioned in historical citations, dating back to Biblical times and reign of King Solomon. It is widely believed that the teak wood used in King Solomon’s throne was from Quilon.

Teresapalli Copper plate

The first identified reference about Kollam comes from the “Teresapalli Copper Plate or Kottayam Cheppedu” of 849 C E. This epigraphic record explains about the rights, land grants, tax exceptions and other such measures granted by Venad king Ayyanadikal Thiruvadikal to Iso Tapir, the chief of the trade guilds “Achuvannam” and “Manigramam”. He is also credited with the construction of St. Teresa’s church at Kurakkeni Kollam and is also considered to have been the chief of Syrian Christians at Kollam.

According to the first “cheppedu” Iso Tapir was given the permission to build the church and along with it, was granted the control over certain households. The members of these households were exempted from paying taxes like “Meniponnu”, “Kappan”, “Panjakkandi” etc. to the royal government.

The second “Cheppedu” was signed by Ayyanadikal Thiruvadikal and Ramathiruvadi and the record deals with the granting of more men to the Church. Besides, the church was given the right to collect taxes from the households under their control and it was also made

clear that the church and its properties should be protected by Achuvannam, Manigramam and Arunnuvattar.

Kollam Era

The defining era of Kerala began on August 15th, 825 C.E. Initially, Kollam era or “Kolamba varsham” was followed in Kerala, Ceylon, Tirunelveli, Madurai etc. There are different theories roaming around regarding the origin of the era. Historians like William Hunter opined that the era might have started so as to commemorate some kind of a renovation activity associated with the region. Dr. Buchanan, Warrel, Cunningham etc. recorded that the Kollam era might have been the recurrence of the “Parasuramabdam”.

UllorParameswaraAiyerinhis “KeralaSahithyacharithrathram” recorded that Kollam era might have been started as an alternative for Kali era while N A Nilakanta Sastri opined that the beginning of the new calendar would have been to commemorate the destruction of Venad by Kulothunga Chola. In addition to these theories, there are some other religious interpretations roaming around the historical world which directly or indirectly tries to solidify the heritage of the respective religious thoughts. The era is also ascribed another name; “Udayavarmabdam” which pertains to the fact that the calendar was started by king Udayamarthandavarman.

Rameswaram temple inscription

Kollam king Ramar Thiruvadikal is ascribed with the formulation of the Rameswaram inscription of 1102 C.E. The inscription deals with the granting of certain rights to the temple authorities as an act of penance for the supposed atrocities committed against Brahmins at Nilamel in Kollam, by Venad ruler Veerakeralavarman. Sankunni Menon’s “Thiruvithamcore Charithram” explains about this granting. The inscription can be viewed as clear evidence suggesting the growing influence of Namboothiri Brahmins upon Kerala rulers even as early as 12th century C.E.

Colonial Kollam

Quilon was first colonized by the Portuguese forces in 1502 when they set up a trading center at Thangasseri. They reached Kollam on the request of the queen for boosting spice trade. A popular notion among scholars is that colonial era might have started in India with

the Portuguese entry. Even though there were little skirmishes between Arabs and Portuguese, their control continued on till Dutch forces started exhibiting their influence in Kollam. Dutch forces established their military troop in Quilon and gradually West Quilon came to be referred to as “Dutch Quilon”. But with the defeat of Dutch forces at the hands of Marthanda Varma, and their return to their homeland leaving everything behind, British forces took over the charge.

Under the rule of different colonial powers, Kollam started witnessing a tide of changes especially in the fields of medicine, transportation, trade and education. The region was then a part of the Travancore royal principality which was in turn under the control of British government through residency. A large number of novel initiatives were introduced in the region by the collaboration of the Travancore royal government and the British administration. The first train service of Travancore ran from Sengottai to Punalur and the innocent people of Kollam who for the first time saw this machine were so afraid and dumbstruck that they labeled it as “Dhoomashakudasaran”. But later this railway network expanded to Thiruvananthapuram and Kottayam.

Kollam saw the establishment of the first airport of Travancore in Ashramam in 1933. The first landing of a flight in Travancore also occurred in Kollam’s “Peeranki Maithanam” in 1932. Besides these achievements, the region also saw some more “firsts” such as the first book to be published from India was from Quilon. “Doctrina Christam” by Francis Xavier was published on October 20, 1578.

C E 1329 saw the establishment of the first Catholic diocese of India in Quilon, but due to certain misdealing the first Bishop took charge only in 1845 CE. The colonial period saw the visit of certain important personalities to Kollam. These eminent men include Madras governor Lord Harris, Prince of Wales and Viceroy Lord Curzon. All the three were impressed by the beauty and splendor of Ashtamudi River and similar other natural wonders of Kollam. Lord Curzon had even taken an initiative in alienating the unequal educational access to people from downtrodden castes. In memory of his visit a road in Kollam is still termed as “Curzon Road”.

Struggle for an Egalitarian Society

Nineteenth century and twentieth century witnessed reformatory and revolutionary struggles brewing along the breadth and length of Kerala crying for the establishment of a society guided by equality, humanity, fraternity, progressive values and rationality. Personalities like Sree Narayana Guru, Chattampi Swamikal, Aiyya Vaikunta Swami etc. and organizations like SNDP, NSS, Yogakshema Sabha were the pioneers who paved way for the growth and progress Kerala achieved in the later years. Among these organizations, the headquarters of SNDP is still in Kollam.

The two written petitions submitted to British administration by two diverse groups were stepping stones to the fight for equality. The first one was Malayalee memorial formulated on the initiative of G P Pillai and submitted to the king in 1891 against the appointment of Tamil Brahmins to the government posts at the cost of sidelining educated natives of Travancore. The second petition was Ezhava Memorial formulated on the model of Malayalee Memorial by Dr. Palpu and submitted to the king on September 1896 requesting to be granted the right to equal education and equal job opportunities.

The people of Kollam were so into revolutionary and reformatory ideas that many Kollam natives including A K Pillai, K G Kunjukrishna Pillai, Neelakantan Sastri etc. actively participated in Vaikom Satyagraha and other similar egalitarian struggles. The most important event in the revolutionary history of the region occurred during 1915 in the form of “Perinadu Lahala” which manifested itself into a blood spewing riot between upper caste Nairs and lower caste Pulayas. Upper caste men started physically attacking poor Pulaya farmers and manual labourers and also burnt their homes. Perinadu, Chennithala and Mavelikkara were the focal points of the struggle. As an extension to this riot occurred the “Kallumala struggle” under the leadership of Dalit leader Gopaladas wherein by Pulaya women discarded their caste imposed custom of wearing “Kallumala” or necklace made of stones. This incident paved way for the growth of self-respect and reliance among Dalit women.

Towards Independence

The independence struggles and national movements of Indian leaders started making their inroads into Kerala and many natives began actively participating in the revolts and boycotts. Gandhiji's and Indian National Congress's (INC) call for boycott of foreign goods and governmental duties had its reverberations in Kerala too. INC had strong roots in Kollam. A K Pillai had established units of INC at Kollam and Thiruvananthapuram in 1919. In addition to A K Pillai, there were more prominent congress leaders and freedom fighters in the region like P K Padmanabha Pillai, C Kesavan, T M Vargheese, E V Krishna Pillai, C V Kunjuraman and R Sankar. The meeting of INC was held at Sasthamcotta in 1927 under the auspicious of Kumbalath Sanku Pillai. In order to achieve responsible government, State Congress was formulated with Kollam native C V Kunjuraman as the chairperson. With the formation of this state congress, the struggles for responsible government became more vocal. "Peeranki Maithanam" was the face of the struggles and there was wide participation of workers, students and advocates in this 'samaram'. British administration tried to crush the revolts using arms and ammunitions.

Gandhiji had made visits to Kollam town, his first visit was in 1925 March 12th for the purpose of being a part of the revolutionarily relevant Vaikom Satyagraha. While in the town he had made a historical speech in "Peeranki Maithanam" regarding the perilousness and absurdity of the practice of untouchability and unapproachability. His next visit was in 1927 October 10th for amassing fund for the Khadi Board. He was accompanied by Kasthurba Gandhi. Gandhiji's Kollam visit of 1934 was meant for emancipating 'harijans' and in all his speeches he made comments on the senselessness of the atrocities committed by the upper caste men on the downtrodden class. Mahatma's last arrival to Kollam was in 1937, on his way from Madras and during his reception meeting he made a prolific speech on the philosophical thoughts of Hinduism.

After Independence

Industrial Growth and Decline

Kollam was once a focal centre of large- and small-scale

industries owned by both government and private entities. The town had become a hub of manufacturing and production and gradually became the forerunner in trade and commerce of Kerala. The beginning of this trade bloom occurred during the days of monarchy. Cotton mill and H&C were the pioneers in this list of enterprises.

The establishment of Kundara Ceramic factory by the government in 1940 was a milestone in the development of Kollam town. But the face of Quilon was always its cashew industries from the days of the inception of the first cashew industry in Kollam in 1925 by Joseph Pereira and Sathyanarayanamoorthi. Later on, cashew factories began mushrooming in each nook and corner of the district. Imports and exports counting to crores of rupees were carried out between Kollam and other trade links. Monazite factory, Titanium and sponge factories also became part of the trade map of the region. But unfortunately, the industrial sector of the district is in very pathetic condition mainly due to the lack of proper governmental aid, deficiency in incentives, trade union activities, difficulty in recruiting workers and recurring strikes. The nationalization policy of the communist government also prompted the industries to shift their location from Kerala to Tamil Nadu.

Recently, the tourism industry has been showing a striking progress in Kollam. A network connecting all the important historical structures, architectural monuments, resorts, waterfalls, beaches, hill stations and cave temples has been formulated for boosting tourism.

Tourist Attractions

Palaruvi waterfalls near Aryankavu is an environmental wonder which attracts thousands of tourists annually from all over the world. Jadayupara near Chadayamangalam has been recently renovated and developed into a tourist hub and adventurous spot. The rock structure holds a prominent place in the religious history too as the structure is associated with the mythical fight between Jadayu and Ravan for retrieving Sita. Senduruni Wildlife Sanctuary in Pathanapuram, is visited by throngs of people as the place is known for its rich fauna. Kottavasal and Tenmala Eco-tourism project area

attracts thousands of tourists annually because of its mesmerizing environment and breathtaking viewpoints. Tenmala eco-tourism is characterized by world famous adventure zones and diverse fauna varieties. President trophy Jalolsavam too attracts a lot of people to Kollam.

Trade Union Activities

With the industrialization of Kollam, capitalistic forces began showing their true colors and they gradually started crushing the workers through inhumane measures such as low wages, lack of proper working hours and conditions. And as a reaction to this atrocity, workers began to assemble themselves into unions and welfare organizations. There were numerous trade union leaders like Janardhanan Nair, T M Prabha, T P Gopalan, M N Govindan Nair, T K Divakaran etc. who fought relentlessly for the rights of workers. And as a result of these innumerable struggles, Kollam became the first region in India where factory workers were granted bonus for their work.

Educational Achievements

Since Travancore rulers were educated themselves, they took initiative in spreading education and awareness in their principality by working in collaboration with the British government and missionaries. It was during Rani GouriParvathy Bhai's reign that the decision was taken to establish government schools teaching the mother tongue. The first Malayalam school of Kollam was established in 1867 CE. And following this, many more institutions were established. A large number of convents and girls' schools were also set up. Now, the region can boast of numerous prestigious institutions including SN College, Fathima Mata College, D B College, NSS College, TKM College and innumerable schools of high order and discipline.

Publishing History

More than half a dozen newspapers were published from Kollam, but most of them survived for only a few months or years. Chandrika which got published in 1895 was one of the first newspapers to come out of Kollam. Following it, Swarajyam, Panchajanyam, Desabhimani, Prabhatham, Janayugam, Pouran etc. started its

publication from Kollam. In spite of having a strong press and publication history, present day Kollam has only three newspapers with their edition service in the district.

Important Personalities

Kollam has given birth to many novelists, poets, storytellers and actors who have made a mark for themselves in the map of Kerala's cultural history. This list include such eminent personalities like O N V Kurup, Tirunelloor Karunakaran, Puthussery Ramachandran, K C Siva Pillai, Azhakath Padmanabha Kurup, Kureppuzha Sreekumar, C P Kesava Vaidyan, Lalithambika Antharjanam, D Vinayachandran, K P Appan etc. Some prominent historians too have taken birth in Kollam like Ilamkulam Kunjan Pillai, Shooranad Kunjan Pillai, P Bhaskaranunni, Puthuppalli Raghavan and V Lakshmanan.

Law Enforcement

The law and order of Kollam is maintained through policing and the agency responsible for keeping up the discipline and punish system of the land is Kerala Police. Kollam City Police is the first ISO 9001 certified law enforcement agency in Kerala and the second in India. They make sure of the smooth functioning of law enforcement through the 17 police stations under its control. Even though there is systematic policing there is something lagging behind, especially in the case of women safety, theft, drug peddling and attack on people leading secluded life.

Conclusion

Kollam or Quilon had always left a mark of its own in every field, be it education or trade or arts or politics. Before the formation of Travancore, Kollam was an important port and also the most important town of South India. But with the merging of Kollam with the royal principality, the port and town lost its prominence. Moreover, the recurring colonization of the land by various imperial powers too affected the integrity of the pace. Even though foreign rule had helped the region in developing its education, transportation and trade, it had also created skirmishes and revolts mainly due to its monopolization tendencies.

Towards and after independence, Quilon had achieved flying

colors in industrial production and manufacturing, but everything collapsed within a short span of time and thus the region has now become a cemetery of abandoned factories and other structures. Many revolutionary and gender equality movements had been organized and led in Kollam. Womens' rights activist like J Devika hail from Kollam. Nowadays, the depth of crime against women, children and old people are on the rise in the district but most importantly the ratio of developmental projects allotted to the region is also low. Kollam has become a shadow of other developing districts with a story to boast of its ancient heritage and glory.

Reference

- Aiyar, S Ramanath. Progressive Travancore. Anantha Rama Varma, 1923.
Bhaskaranunni, P. Kollathinte Charitram. Kollam Public Library, 1994.
Gangadharan, T K. History of Kerala. University of Calicut, 2012.
Logan, William. Malabar Manual. Madras Government Press, 1906.
Menon, Sankunni. History of Travancore. Kerala Gazetteers, 1983.
Menon, A Sreedhara. A Survey of Kerala History. DC Books, 2015.
Pachumoothathu. Thiruvithamcore Charitram. Betascript Publishing, 2010.
Pillai, T K Velu. Travancore State Manual. Government of Travancore, 1940.
Pillai, Shooranad Kunjan. Malabar: In the Eyes of Travelers. Kerala Bhasha Institute, 2018.
Sadasivan, T D. Kollam: Charithrathile Nazhikakallukal. Kerala Bhasha Institute, 2012.

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,